

Cybercrime Analysis using Machine Learning Algorithms: Decision Tree, Naïve Bayes, Random Forest and K-Nearest Neighbor

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Abstract—Cybercrime is defined as a crime committed through the use of a computer or network. Cybercrime is growing day by day; it is one of the main crimes executed via internet and technology. Cyberattack can lead to loss of a lot of sensitive data, including personal information, password and credit card numbers. Machine Learning has arisen as a major technique in the field of cybercrime protection. Through design distinguishing proof, ongoing cybercrime planning and broad entrance testing, AI proactively gets rid of digital dangers and fortifies security foundation. In this study, we use four machine learning algorithms: Decision Tree, Random Forest, Naïve Bayes and K-Nearest Neighbor to analyze cybercrime. Among the used cybercrimes Random Forest and Decision tree proved to be the most accurate.

Keywords— cybercrime, Machine Learning, Decision Tree, Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbor

I. INTRODUCTION

Cybercrime is characterized as a wrong-doing perpetrated utilizing a computer or any other device connected via the internet. Cybercrime can endanger an individual's security and monetary prosperity. According to the 2014 survey, the world economy was hurt by \$445 billion consistently. According to Cybersecurity Ventures' estimate from 2016, worldwide cybercrime misfortunes could go for 6 trillion dollars every year by 2021 and \$10.5 trillion every year by 2025. Cybercrime charges almost 1% of worldwide GDP, or 600 billion dollars, every year, as per a review gave in 2018 from the Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) related to McAfee.

ML is a category of human-made logical thinking that allow programming applications to make development for forecast precision without being explicitly intended to do as such. To figure new result values, ML calculations utilizes authentic data from dataset obtained from the public domain as information. The calculation's feedback and result are both known. The goal of this study is to analyze the cybercrime dataset using various ML algorithms: Decision Tree, Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbor and Naïve Bayes.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Olta Llahi [1] The development of examination procedures targeting separating information from wrongdoing records to more readily figure out criminal way of behaving and, at last, forestall future violations has come about because of the expansion in wrongdoing information recording joined with information examination. The goal of this research is to look at crime analysis by looking at how data mining tools might be used to forecast and prevent crime.

Neil Shah [2] The creators brought up that the need for an expectation framework has built as society and the economy have brought about new type of violations. Wrongdoing patterns and expectation innovation called Malacologist, as well as a unique time wrapping procedure, are depicted, considering the conjecture of wrong doing and the capture of the genuine culprit.

Steven Walczak [3] The article discusses and evaluates current research on the use of neural networks for crime forecasting and other police decision-making problems. To demonstrate the use of neural networks in enforcing decision-making, models were constructed to predict certain types of crime using location and time information, as well as to forecast a crime's location when given the crime and time of day. The article discusses and evaluates current research on the use of neural networks for crime forecasting and other police decision-making problems. To show the use of neural networks to police, models were constructed to predict various types of crime using location and time information.

Vikas Grover [4] Physically disentangling the intrinsic complexities inside police information is a troublesome work for a police examiner, and this challenge is exacerbated when the investigation is done by a group, as every part might not have exceedingly significant realities and important data might be lost. Crime analysts and analysts have been utilizing their capacities and information attempt to guess when and where the following group of violations will happen for quite a while, with various levels of progress. The greatness of

wrongdoing and current guilty parties' expanded mindfulness put a burden on conventional strategies.

M. Raja Suguna[5]. Crime analysis aids police and investigation agencies in predicting future incident and taking necessary actions. The hotspots have been found; a hotspot is a set of coordinates in which more crimes occur frequently. Following the identification of hotspots, greater emphasis is placed on certain crime-prone locations in order to prevent and control crime.

III. MOTIVATION

Cybercrime is quickly becoming a major concern. Governments, police forces, and intelligence agencies around the world have begun to respond. Cybercrime is any illegal action that done computers or computer networks are utilized as an instrument of crime, a location, or a target for criminal conduct, and can be electronic cracking to denial-of-service attacks. It can also refer to crimes involving the employing of computers or networks to facilitate criminal conduct. Illegal access to computers, data manipulation, data destruction, and intellectual property theft are the most conducted types of computer crime. In the context of countries security, cybercrime might take the shape of activism, classic espionage, or information warfare, among the various other things.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The obtained datasets were initially preprocessed and merged. The test set is used to evaluate the classification models. In addition to accuracy, metrics such as precision, recall and f1-scores are measured. Random forest, Decision tree, K-nearest neighbor and Naïve Bayes are used to analyze the crime.

- a. **Collecting Data:** The dataset was obtained from the internet. The attributes of the dataset were used to train the model. The dataset had 1.5 crore rows and 26 columns.
 - b. **Cleaning Data:** The dataset obtained was then further cleaned. The dataset had 26 features initially, which was way too much to process as the dataset was large. We cleaned the data using feature selection, by removing the unwanted features and by doing so making the dataset smaller and more comfortable to work with. Using feature selection, we take just 5 features into consideration.
 - **Machine Learning:** Machine learning may accelerate the processing and analyzing of data, making it a powerful tool for analytics projects. Predictive analytics techniques that use machine learning may train on increasingly larger datasets and do deeper analysis on numerous factors with modest deployment changes. Machine Learning is being utilized to access cybercrime in India over a period of years. The cybercrime dataset is analyzed using supervised learning methods such as k- Nearest Neighbor, Random Forest, Naive Bayes, and Decision trees.
1. **Random Forest Algorithm-** Random Forest is a

notable machine learning calculation that utilizes the managed learning strategy. In machine learning, it tends to be used for both order and relapse issues. It depends on outfit realizing, which is a strategy for coordinating various classifiers to take care of a mind-boggling issue and increment the model's presentation. " Irregular Forest is a predictor that uses the normal to improve the expected accuracy of a dataset by using numerous choice trees on different sets of the dataset. " As indicated by the name. The accuracy obtained by the algorithm is 0.99

2. **Naïve Bayes Algorithm-** The algorithm strategy is a managed investigating procedure for tending to grouping issues that depends on the theorem. It is for the most part used in text characterization errands it requires a huge preparation dataset. The Classifier is an uncomplicated and functional classification method that help in the growth of fast machine learning models capable of making quick predictions. It's a probabilistic classification technique, meaning it makes a prediction based on the likelihood of an item. The accuracy obtained by the algorithm is 0.98
3. **Decision Tree Classification Algorithm-**It is a supervised learning technique that might be used to take care of grouping and relapse issues, but it is usually utilized to tackle characterization issues. Inner hubs address dataset ascribes, branches address choice guidelines, and each leaf hub gives the end in this tree-organized classifier. Decision Trees are intended to reflect human reasoning skills while simply deciding, simplifying them to appreciate. Since the choice tree has a tree-like shape, the reasoning overdo it is easy to study. The accuracy obtained by the algorithm is 0.99
4. **K- Nearest Neighbor algorithm** –is a Supervised Learning technique what's more, is one of the most important for ML calculations. The K- NN algorithm expects that the new case/information and existing cases are comparative and spots the new case in the class that is generally like the current classes. The K- NN technique stores generally accessible information and orders another information guide in light of its comparability toward the current information. The accuracy obtained by the algorithm is 0.75

V. BUILD MODEL

The model building is the main step in the cybercrime prediction. While building the model user use the algorithms. The steps are:

1. Import the packages that are necessary.

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
import sqlite3
import argparse
import json
import pprint
import requests
import sys
import urllib
import os
from urllib.error import HTTPError
from urllib.parse import quote
from urllib.parse import urlencode
```

2. Then clean the dataset

```
crime_df.to_csv("crimedataclean.csv",index=False)
```

```
crime_df = pd.read_csv("crimedataclean.csv")
crime_df.head()
```

Area ID	Reporting District	Crime Code Description	Victim Age	Premise Code	
0	12	1241	Ransomware	30.0	502.0
1	20	2071	Phishing	0.0	101.0
2	18	1823	Phishing	12.0	101.0
3	18	1803	Phishing	0.0	101.0
4	21	2133	VANDALISM - MISDEAMEANOR (\$399 OR UNDER)	84.0	501.0

3. Then, fit and transform train and test set.

```
clf = clf.fit(X, y)
```

4. Using Decision Tree

```
from sklearn import tree
clf = tree.DecisionTreeClassifier()
clf = clf.fit(X, y)
dtac = clf.score(X, y)
b = clf.predict(X)
print("Accuracy Using Decision Tree")
print("Accuracy :",accuracy_score(y,b))
print("Precision :", precision_score(y,b, average='macro'))
print("Recall :", recall_score(y,b,average='macro'))
print("F1 Score :", f1_score(y,b, average='macro'))
```

5. Using Random Forest.

```
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
rf = RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=20)
rf = rf.fit(X, y)
b = rf.predict(X)
print("Accuracy Using Random Forest")
print("Accuracy :",accuracy_score(y,b))
print("Precision :", precision_score(y,b, average='macro'))
print("Recall :", recall_score(y,b,average='macro'))
print("F1 Score :", f1_score(y,b, average='macro'))
```

6. Using Naïve Bayes.

```
from sklearn.naive_bayes import GaussianNB
gnb = GaussianNB()
gnb.fit(X, y)
b = gnb.predict(X)
print("Accuracy Using Naive Bayes")
print("Accuracy :",accuracy_score(y,b))
print("Precision :", precision_score(y,b, average='macro'))
print("Recall :", recall_score(y,b,average='macro'))
print("F1 Score :", f1_score(y,b, average='macro'))
```

7. Using K-NN

```
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
knn = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=7)
knn.fit(X, y)
knnac = knn.score(X,y)
b = knn.predict(X)
print("Accuracy Using K-NN")
print("Accuracy :",accuracy_score(y,b))
print("Precision :", precision_score(y,b, average='macro'))
print("Recall :", recall_score(y,b,average='macro'))
print("F1 Score :", f1_score(y,b, average='macro'))
```

VI. RESULT

The outcome demonstrates that utilizing some features from the given dataset, a specific crime can be analyzed and predicted using the features like area id, reporting district victim age premise code. Four algorithms are used here: K-Nearest Neighbor, Decision Tree, Naive Bayes, and Random Forest. The Decision tree algorithm is capable of making accurate and reliable predictions. Various sorts of crime are included in the dataset.

```
Accuracy Using Decision Tree
Accuracy : 0.9956666666666667
Precision : 0.992
Recall : 0.9976991150442478
F1 Score : 0.994371045304986
```

```
Accuracy Using Random Forest
Accuracy : 0.9953333333333333
Precision : 0.9919726962457338
Recall : 0.9974028187479514
F1 Score : 0.9942086898821602
```

```
Accuracy Using K-NN
Accuracy : 0.988
Precision : 0.9177283639016482
Recall : 0.9523727839737706
F1 Score : 0.9315712193360212
```

```
Accuracy Using Naive Bayes
Accuracy : 0.759
Precision : 0.8846526636054994
Recall : 0.8978140185658731
F1 Score : 0.8818672227570633
```


Figure 1: Accuracy of various algorithms

VII. CONCLUSION

Cybercrimes are indictable offences and misdemeanors that use computers, commission instruments, or are linked to the widespread use of computers. Child pornography, cyberstalking, identity theft, cyber laundering, credit card theft, cyber terrorism, drug sales, data leakage, sexually explicit content, phishing, and other forms of cyber hacking are all examples of common cybercrimes. They usually result in a data leak, a security breach, a commercial loss, financial fraud, or property damage at public and government buildings. As a result, this research examines cybercrime detection and prevention approaches in depth. It begins by examining the many types of cybercrime and the hazards they pose to computer systems' privacy and security. In this paper we use four different Machine Learning to predict the cybercrimes based on the area where the crime was committed, the time and various other features are also taken

into consideration. Among the four used algorithms the Decision Tree and the Random Forest were the most accurate and the Naïve Bayes was the least accurate algorithm.

VIII. REFERENCES

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